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SYNTHESIS AND STUDY OF COMPOUNDS OF TYPE $\text{LaB}^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ (B^{V} -Sb, Bi)

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ABSTRACT

Using methods of physicochemical analysis, the mode of synthesis of $\text{LaB}^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ (B^{V} -Sb, Bi) compounds indirectly was established. The $\text{LaB}^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ compound crystallizes in the tetradymite structural type with space group $D_{3d}^5-R_{3m}$ hexagonal cell parameters for LaSbTe_3 $a = 4.24 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 30.64 \text{ \AA}$, $c/a = 7.1$ and for LaBiTe_3 $a = 4.36 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 30.70 \text{ \AA}$, $c/a = 7.04$.

They are narrow-gap n-type semiconductors, for LaSbTe_3 $\Delta E = 0.18 \text{ eV}$; $d_{\text{pycn.}} = 6.62 \text{ g/sm}^3$, $d_{\text{rent}} = 6.69 \text{ g/sm}^3$, $H\mu = 2110 \text{ MPa}$ and for LaBiTe_3 $\Delta E = 0.21 \text{ eV}$,

$d_{\text{pycn.}} = 7.15 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $d_{\text{rent}} = 7.20 \text{ g/sm}^3$, $H\mu = 1955 \text{ MPa}$

Keywords: synthesis, research, indirect way, crystallization, semiconductor.

Introduction

Recently, a large number of new ternary chemical compounds involving KSM have been synthesized and studied with the properties of semiconductor chalcogenides, rare earth elements and group V elements, as well as phases based on them, are promising substances for working as topological insulators and thermoelectric materials [1-10].

Purpose of the study

In this work, the goal was to synthesize a compound of the $\text{LaB}^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ type. (B^{V} -Sb, Bi).

Experimental part

Synthesis of $\text{LaB}^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$. (B^{V} -Sb, Bi) is carried out by fusing an equimolar amount of the original components.

Sb_2Te_3 (Bi_2Te_3) with lanthanum chlorides (LaCl_3). Sb_2Te_3 (Bi_2Te_3) is obtained by fusing stoichiometric amounts of elements using the ampoule method [11]. For this purpose, antimony and bismuth B-4, Tellurium TA- 2, reagent grade lanthanum chlorides are used.

The compound Sb_2Te_3 (Bi_2Te_3) has a rhombohedral layered structure of the tetradymite type ($\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_2\text{S}$), belonging to the space group $D_{3d}^5-R_{3m}$ [12] and has the following lattice parameters (for Sb_2Te_3 , $a = 4.25 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 30.487 \text{ \AA}$, $c/a = 7.08$, and for Bi_2Te_3 $a = 4.373 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 30.487 \text{ \AA}$, $c/a = 6.97$). They are semiconductors with a small band gap (for Sb_2Te_3 0.19 eV , and for Bi_2Te_3

0.15 eV), high thermal emf coefficient. and low thermal conductivity. At room temperature it has n-type electrical conductivity [10-15].

Stoichiometric amounts of $\text{Sb}_2(\text{Bi}_2)\text{Te}_3$ and LaCl_3 were thoroughly crushed, mixed and placed in a quartz beaker, which is placed in a quartz reactor with an outlet tube for the BiCl_3 released during the reaction. Before synthesis, the reactor was purged with an inert gas (Ar) and connected to a water-jet pump through the water seal of the Tishchenko flask. The required temperature was achieved using a homemade crucible furnace in which the reactor was placed [19]. The optimal synthesis mode was established experimentally. Temperature $630-750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3-5 hours.

Results and its discussion

During the fusion process of $\text{B}_2^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ and CaCl_3 , a complex chemical interaction occurs. As a result, powdery and gaseous products were obtained.

X-ray, thermal and chemical analyzes showed that the interaction of $\text{B}_2^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ with LaCl_3 can be summarized by the reaction equation:

The reaction products were identified by chemical, differential thermal (DTA) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses. The results of the analysis are shown in table 1.

Table 1.

Results of chemical analyzes of $\text{LaB}^{\text{V}}\text{Te}_3$ compound.

Compounds	Chemical composition								
	Calculated, weight, %				Found, weight %				
	La	Sb	Bi	Te	La	Sb	Bi	Te	Component ratio
LaSbTe_3	25,73	17,92		56,33	25,71	17,90		56,30	1:1:1
LaBiTe_3	19,01		28,59	52,36	19,0		28,68	52,36	1:1:1

Samples obtained in the form of ingots and annealed at 650°C for two weeks were subjected to complex methods of physicochemical analysis. A comparison of the diffraction patterns of the compounds showed that they are isostructural and crystallize in the hexagonal system with space group $D_{3d}^5 - R_{3m}$.

Table 2 shows the lattice periods and some physicochemical properties of these compounds. Electrical conductivity and thermo-emf were studied. these compounds at room temperature and it was found that they are narrow-gap n-type semiconductors. The band gap is equal for $LaSbTe_3$ $\Delta E = 0.22$ eV; for $LaBiTe_3$ $\Delta E = 0.19$ eV.

Table 2

Results of some physicochemical and crystal chemical properties of LaB^VTe_3 compounds

Compounds	Singonia	Structural type	Lattice period, Å			Density g/sm ³		Formation temperature, K	H _m , MPa
			a	b	c/a	d rent	d pycn.		
$LaSbTe_3$	rhombic	Bi_2Te_2S	4,24	30,64	7,21	6,69	6,62	1100	2750
$LaBiTe_3$	n	n	4,36	30,70	7,04	7,9	7,5	925	2370

Conclusion

As a result of research, a mode for the synthesis of LaB^VTe_3 (Bv-Sb, Bi) compounds by indirect route has been established. The LaB^VTe_3 compound crystallizes in the tetradymite structural type with space group $D_{3d}^5-R_{3m}$, hexagonal cell parameters for $LaSbTe_3$ $a = 4.24$ Å, $b = 30.64$ Å, $c/a = 7.1$ and for $LaBiTe_3$ $a = 4.36$ Å $b=30.70$ Å, $c/a=7.04$.

It was revealed that LaB^VTe_3 (Bv-Sb, Bi) compounds are narrow-gap n-type semiconductors.

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